

GRAMMAR-TRANSLATION METHOD ON ACQUIRING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND ITS DISADVANTAGES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7456282>

Abstract:

The goal of this research is to investigate the effect of using Grammar-Translation method on acquiring English as a foreign language. Translation method is a method of learning any foreign language by the practice of translating or converting the sentences from target language to the mother tongue or vice versa. Today mostly teachers establishments are too prone to implement this method into their practice.

Key words:

Grammatical rules, GTM, goal, target language, mother tongue, skill, translation

Аннотация:

Целью данного исследования является исследование влияния использования метода грамматики-перевода на приобретение английского языка в качестве иностранного языка. Метод перевода - это метод изучения любого иностранного языка путем практики перевода или преобразования предложений с целевого языка на родной язык или наоборот. Сегодня в основном в основном преподаватели являются слишком склонными для реализации этого метода в свою практику.

Ключевые слова: грамматические правила, GTM, цель, изучаем язык, родной язык, талант, перевод

Introduction

As with many other methods and approaches, Grammar Translation tended to be referred to in the past tense as if it no longer existed and had died out to be replaced world-wide by the fun and motivation of the communicative classroom. If we examine the principal features of Grammar Translation, however, we will see that not only has it not disappeared but that many of its characteristics have been central to language teaching throughout the ages and are still valid today. The grammar translation method is a method of teaching foreign languages derived from the classical method of teaching Greek and Latin. In grammar-translation classes, students learn grammatical rules and then apply those rules by translating sentences between the target language and the native language. Advanced students may be required to translate whole texts word-for-word. The

method has two main goals: to enable students to read and translate literature written in the target language, and to further students' general intellectual development. GTM focuses on the application of grammar and correct sentence structure. This is especially helpful in teaching students how to write and read in another language, allowing them to explore interchangeable words and phrases (i.e., different words for different tenses) more effectively than a verbal teaching method. There are certain types of learner who respond very positively to a grammatical syllabus as it can give them both a set of clear objectives and a clear sense of achievement. Other learners need the security of the mother tongue and the opportunity to relate grammatical structures to mother tongue equivalents. Above all, this type of approach can give learners a basic foundation upon which they can then build their communicative skills. This method is effective, but it also has its drawbacks. One of the major disadvantages of GTM is that it restricts the skills of speaking and listening to a foreign language. The Grammar Translation method puts too much emphasis on reading and writing and neglects listening and speaking. Knowing a large number of grammatical rules cannot ensure that students can use them appropriately in real communicative situation. The reading skill is exercised over and over in the context of translation and this can lower students potential.

About four decades ago Edward Anthony (1963) identified three levels of conceptualization and organization, which he termed approach, method, and technique. An approach, according to Anthony was a set of assumptions dealing with the nature of language, learning and teaching. Method was described as an overall plan for systematic presentation of language based upon a selected approach. Techniques were the specific activities manifested in the classroom that were consistent with a method and therefore were in harmony with an approach as well. A couple of decades later, Richards and Rodgers (1982, 1986) proposed a reformulation of the concept of "method". Anthony's approach, method, and technique were renamed, respectively, approach, design, and procedure, with a super ordinate term to describe this three-step process, now called "method". A method, according to Richards and Rodgers, was "an umbrella term for the specification and interrelation of theory and practice". An approach defines assumption, beliefs, and theories about the nature of language and language learning. Designs specify the relationship of those theories to classroom materials and activities. Procedures are the techniques and practices that are derived from one's approach and design. English language learning and teaching has undergone a tremendous change over the period of time,

particularly during the twentieth century it has witnessed novelty in this field. The grammar translation method is a foreign language teaching methodology derived from classical methods (sometimes called traditional) method in teaching Greek and Latin. The method requires that students translate whole texts word for word and memorize numerous grammatical rules and exceptions as well as enormous vocabulary lists. The goal of this method is to enable students to read and translate literary master pieces and classics. Under the influence of British applied linguists (such as John Firth, M.A.K.Halliday, who stressed the functional and communicative potential of language), sociolinguistics works (Dell Hymes, and W.Labov) and some philosophy work (J. Austin and J. Searle), the communicative method was advocated in language teaching. It saw the need to focus on communicative proficiency rather than on mere mastering of structures. the purpose of the study. In GTM method the students are not forced to communicate in the target language but in CLT method the students are emphasized to communicate in target language for the daily and teaching learning activities. On the other hand, www.ijsrm.humanjournals.com Citation: Esmaeil Heydari Asl et al. Ijsrm.Human, 2015; Vol. 1 (3): 16-25. 25 GTM method gets the students to analyze the language rather than to use the language (CelceMurcia, 2001, 6). In contrast in the CLT method has the students use the language rather than analyze the language (Larsen-Freeman, 2011, 115). Additionally, the goal of our language learning process is to enhance the students' ability to communicate in the target language. Each of the different methods has contributed new elements and has attempted to deal with some issues of language learning. However, they derived in different historical context, stressed different social and educational needs and have different theoretical consideration. Therefore, in teaching practice, in order to apply these methods effectively and efficiently, practitioners should take these questions in mind: who the learners are, what their current level of language proficiency is, what sort of communicative needs they have, and the circumstances in which they will be using English in the future, and so on. In a word, no single method could guarantee successful results.

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